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Title

Projected health impact of post-discharge malaria chemoprevention among children under the age of five years with severe malarial anaemia in Africa: a modelling analysis

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Projected health impact of post-discharge malaria chemoprevention among children under the age of five years with severe malarial anaemia in Africa: a modelling analysis

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Abstract

Background

Children discharged from hospital after recovery from severe malarial anaemia (SMA) are at high risk of readmission and death in subsequent months. Clinical trial results show that three months of post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PMC) with dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine reduces this risk.

Methods

We developed a compartmental mathematical model describing the daily post-discharge incidence of uncomplicated and severe malaria requiring readmission among a cohort of 0-5 year-old children. We fitted the model to PMC and placebo groups from nine trial hospitals in areas of moderate-to-intense malaria transmission in Uganda and Kenya using Bayesian methods. The cohort model was then embedded within a full population model of SMA to predict impact of PMC across malaria-endemic African countries.

Findings

The incidence of hospitalised malaria episodes during the first 6 months post-discharge is estimated to be ~23-60 times higher than the average for children of this age, depending on transmission intensity. We estimate that repeat SMA episodes within 6 months of the original episode constitute 18-27% of all SMA episodes in high transmission settings. In the 20 highest-burden countries in Africa, only 2-5 children need to be given PMC to prevent one hospitalised malaria episode, and less than 100 to prevent one death. If all hospitalised cases access PMC, we estimate that 36,000 (range 16,000-82,000) malaria-associated readmissions could be prevented annually, depending on the proportion accessing hospital care.

Interpretation

PMC has high potential impact per child treated across a range of epidemiological settings in Africa.

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Introduction

Severe malarial anaemia (SMA) still contributes substantially to childhood mortality and morbidity in malaria-endemic countries in Africa. *P. falciparum* malaria causes anaemia by triggering severe haemolysis of erythrocytes and suppression of erythropoiesis.¹ In highly endemic areas, around one-third of all hospitalised children may be severely anaemic (Hb<5g/dL)^{2,3} and severe anaemia may contribute to around half of all malaria-attributed deaths.⁴ While malaria transmission has declined in many countries in the past two decades, highly endemic conditions persist in parts of sub-Saharan Africa. 70% of global malaria deaths occurred in just ten countries in Africa in 2020.⁵ These countries are now the focus of the WHO High Burden to High Impact (HBHI) initiative, aimed at accelerating progress in malaria control in the hardest-hit areas.⁵

Between 0.4 and 13% of children with severe anaemia in low and lower-middle-income countries die during the acute hospitalisation phase, but those who survive also remain at high risk of readmission and death following hospital discharge despite having received appropriate care.⁶ A recent meta-analysis found that the odds of death during the first six months after discharge is 72% higher than during hospitalisation and over two times higher than those admitted with other conditions without severe anaemia.⁷ Full haematological recovery from malaria may take around six weeks following treatment, and further malaria re-infections during this period substantially increase the risk of recurrent severe anaemia or death.^{8,9} However, no specific interventions have been widely implemented to tackle this large post-discharge burden of morbidity and mortality among SMA patients.

Post-discharge malaria chemoprevention (PMC), consisting of full treatment courses of long-acting antimalarials administered at pre-determined time intervals after discharge from hospital among children recently admitted with severe anaemia, can reduce the high post-discharge malaria morbidity and mortality. In Malawi, three months of PMC with monthly artemether-lumefantrine achieved a protective efficacy of 41% against the risk of death or all-cause readmission and 49% against clinical malaria in the first 3 months post discharge.¹⁰ More recently, a multicentre trial in Uganda and Kenya showed that three months of PMC with monthly dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine (DP) reduces the risk of deaths or all-cause readmissions by 70% and hospitalised malaria episodes by 87% during the same period.¹¹

As malaria-endemic countries decide whether to implement PMC, there is a need to understand the potential epidemiological impact in settings with varying transmission intensity to support economic evaluation analysis, and planning how PMC could contribute to initiatives such as the HBHI programme. This study characterises the burden of post-discharge malarial disease and estimates the demand for PMC and its potential public health impact in Africa.

Methods

Post-discharge data

Data were from a PMC trial conducted in 2016-2018.¹¹ This randomised, placebo-controlled trial was conducted in nine hospitals in areas with moderate-to-intense perennial malaria transmission in Kenya and Uganda. Participants were 1,049 children under five years of age who were hospitalised for severe anaemia. Children were randomised to receive either a three-day course of DP or placebo at weeks two, six, and ten after discharge from hospital (i.e. 3 x 3 full DP courses = 9 DP doses). All doses except the first were given at home by the caregiver. All children had received the standard in-hospital treatment for severe anaemia: blood transfusion and parenteral artesunate for those with malaria parasites (85% of the patients). They then received a 3-day course of artemether-lumefantrine (AL) at the time of discharge. PMC had most impact on malaria outcomes, not readmissions due to other causes. We therefore focus our analysis on incidence of uncomplicated and hospitalised malaria post-discharge, which were measured by passive follow-

up in study clinics. Malaria cases were hospitalised if they required parenteral treatment, or if they had severe anaemia.

Three further post-discharge studies in Uganda and Malawi were used for model validation, where incidence of hospitalised malaria in children <5 years old without chemoprevention was similarly assessed after admission for severe anaemia.^{10,12,13}

Post-discharge cohort model

We developed a compartmental model to describe the incidence of uncomplicated and hospitalised malaria among the trial cohort of children aged 6–59 months during the six months post-discharge period in PMC and placebo trial arms. We related these outcomes to local transmission intensity in the trial sites and rate of antimalarial treatment for symptomatic malaria episodes as well as PMC, to aid extrapolation to other settings. Full details are given in the Supplementary Information. The model has five states: prophylaxis (P_{DP} and P_{AL}), susceptible (S), treated uncomplicated malaria (T_U), and treated hospitalised malaria (T_S) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Post-discharge cohort model

Boxes represent health states, while arrows and labels show health state transition rates and probabilities of an event. Definitions are given in the text and Table S1. See also supplementary information.

Children enter the model without parasitaemia into state P_{AL} on the day they leave hospital, protected from new infections by AL given at discharge. After prophylaxis, children enter the susceptible state and experience symptomatic malaria (uncomplicated or hospitalised) at a rate equal to the product of the local entomological inoculation rate (EIR), the probability that an infectious bite leads to infection b , the probability of symptoms ϕ and the relative exposure to bites among the post-discharge group of children ξ compared to the average child (Table S1). A proportion θ of symptomatic malaria cases experience disease sufficiently severe to be readmitted to hospital. We assumed that all uncomplicated and severe malaria episodes during follow-up were detected and treated (at rates r_{UM} and r_{SM}). This is a reasonable assumption because the trial reimbursed participant costs of treatment-seeking at study clinics, diminishing financial barriers to care. We do not track asymptomatic cases.

Children randomised to the PMC intervention arm receive up to three full courses of DP at the times specified in the trial. DP prophylaxis is modelled as a probability of prevention of reinfection that declines over time since treatment, with a mean of 28 days, as previously estimated (Figure S1).¹⁴ We allowed for imperfect adherence (Table S1).

Model fitting and validation

We fitted the model to the trial data described above using Bayesian methods and validated against other post-discharge studies which were not used to fit the model. We used semi-informative priors for the EIR in the areas surrounding each hospital, based on the Malaria Atlas Project (MAP) estimates of transmission intensity within 20 km (Table S1).¹⁵ We ran the model for each site and fitted to the daily incidence of uncomplicated and hospitalised malaria simultaneously across sites during 6 months follow up. Since hospitalised malaria numbers were small in some sites, this method borrows information from the uncomplicated malaria cases to inform the underlying EIR. We estimated the maximum incidence of symptomatic malaria (uncomplicated and hospitalised) per infectious bite at the beginning of post-discharge follow up. We estimated how the risk of hospitalised and uncomplicated malaria per infectious bite could decline over time since the original severe anaemia episode, and with increasing EIR. We explored whether the proportion of

cases that require hospitalisation, θ , was different when the children were or were not under active PMC drug protection. All parameters except for EIR were given weakly informative priors (Table S1).

To fit the data, we coded the model in discrete time with a timestep of one day, with transition rates converted to daily probabilities. The model was fitted using Markov chain Monte Carlo methods in the RStan software.¹⁶ We ran 4 chains, each having 5,000 burn-in and 10,000 sampling iterations. All code is available at https://github.com/lucyokell/pmc_model.

Population modelling of PMC demand and impact in different epidemiological settings

To predict PMC demand and impact in different settings, we developed a model describing severe malarial anaemia (SMA) in the total general population of under-five year olds and embedded our post-discharge cohort model within this framework (full details in the Supplementary Appendix). This model additionally allows for SMA cases who do not seek treatment in hospital, as well as lower treatment coverage for uncomplicated malaria and lower adherence to PMC outside the trial setting. For inputs, we used existing models which relate total population incidence of severe malarial anaemia and hospitalised malaria with EIR and prevalence of infection.^{21,22} We generated estimated annual EIR and incidence of total hospitalised malaria for each sub-national region (first administrative unit) of endemic countries in Africa in 2020 using the Imperial College malaria transmission model.²³ We estimated incidence of hospitalised SMA in 0-5 year olds in each region based on a recently published analysis of hospital data (Figure S2).²²

In the full population model (Figure S3), children are stratified into two risk groups: those who experienced SMA within the last 6 months (high-risk) and those who did not (low-risk). When an episode of SMA occurs in low-risk individuals, they move to the high-risk state. The fitted post-discharge cohort model placebo arm was used to describe the incidence of malaria episodes in the high-risk group in the absence of PMC, including SMA episodes. Using estimated total SMA incidence for a given area, the remaining SMA episodes occurring in the low-risk group are calculated. We further stratify SMA cases into those who seek care in hospital versus those who do not. Hospitalised SMA cases are eligible for PMC. After the 6-month period, high-risk individuals return to the low-risk group unless they experience a further episode of SMA. This

model allows for the iterative process of SMA episodes increasing the risk of future SMA episodes, which affects future PMC impact and demand. For hospitalised SMA episodes and non-SMA malaria episodes, case fatality rates of 7.4% and 1.0% were assumed, respectively.^{17,19,20} PMC with DP is incorporated as in the post-discharge cohort model, except that adherence is lower as measured in a recent PMC implementation study¹⁸ (Table S2).

The probability of malaria patients accessing hospital care when required is challenging to estimate and varies between settings. The relationship between malaria transmission intensity and SMA incidence used in our model is based on hospitalised cases in East Africa, but the probability of hospitalisation in these areas is unknown.²² To account for this uncertainty, we varied the probability of hospitalisation between 30, 50, or 70% for sensitivity analysis²⁴ and assumed it could be the same, lower or higher compared to the Paton *et al* study in different settings. We assumed the case fatality rate of malaria cases unable to access hospital would be double the value observed in hospital.²⁰ The model was coded in R as a deterministic discrete-time model and was run to equilibrium, with and without PMC, to estimate the impact of the intervention. The trials and analyses were approved by the ethics committees at the Kenya Medical Research Institute, Makerere University, the Western Norway Regional Committee for Medical and Health Research Ethics, the Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine, the University of Minnesota, and the Uganda National Council of Science and Technology.

Results

Post-discharge cohort model

Our fitted model could capture the total number of observed uncomplicated and hospitalised malaria events in both the post-discharge cohort placebo and PMC trial arms, and the change in daily case incidence over time since discharge (Figure 2). The modelled protective efficacy of PMC, using the previously estimated duration of DP protection of 28 days (Figure S1), was 86% against hospitalised malaria 3-14 weeks post-discharge and 73% against uncomplicated malaria during the same period. This was close to the trial estimates of 87% and 69%, respectively. The differential efficacy against the two outcomes was because the percentage of symptomatic malaria cases that were hospitalised was estimated by the model at 39% (95% credible interval (CrI) 36-42%) (Table S1) among children not under active PMC protection, but this dropped to 25% (95%

CrI 17-34%) among children who had taken recent PMC. The risk of uncomplicated and hospitalised malaria per infectious bite in the placebo group declined over time since discharge (Figure 2 and Figure S4). The incidence of uncomplicated and hospitalised malaria increased with EIR, but the risk of these outcomes per infectious bite decreased (Figures 3 & S5). Three previous post-discharge studies which were not used during model fitting^{10,12,13} showed a similar or slightly lower incidence of post-discharge hospitalised malaria than predicted by our model, given the local EIR (Figure 3B).

The incidence of hospitalised malaria was strikingly high in the post-discharge placebo group compared to the average in the general population of 0-5-year olds, as estimated in other studies²⁵ and by our transmission model²³ (Figure 3B). The incidence of hospitalised malaria in the placebo group was ~39-60 times higher than in the general population during post-discharge weeks 3-14 in settings with EIR>10, and was still 23-36 fold higher in weeks 15-25. This high incidence suggests persistent vulnerability beyond the end of the PMC intervention at week 14. The incidence of uncomplicated malaria was 1.2-2.5 times higher than expected in the general population of the same age in weeks 3-14. The total incidence of symptomatic malaria episodes (uncomplicated and hospitalised) was more than the expected incidence of infectious bites in 0-5 year olds in four trial sites, suggestive of higher exposure to mosquitoes in this group (Figure S6).

Figure 2: Model fits to trial data.

Comparison of the number of malaria cases from the trial and model predictions across all sites. (A) Uncomplicated (UM) and hospitalised malaria (SM) in weeks 3-14 and 15-25 post discharge in PMC (left, blue) and placebo (right, black) trial arms. Error bars show 95% credible intervals (CrI) of model predictions (B) Cumulative daily number of hospitalised malaria cases by time since discharge after the original SMA episode in placebo (black) and PMC (blue) trial arms; solid line=data, dashed line and shaded area=model fit and 95% CrI. (C) As B, for uncomplicated malaria cases. See also Figure S7.

Figure 3 (A) Relationship between prior estimated EIR values in adults and incidence of uncomplicated malaria 3-14 weeks post-discharge in 0–5-year-old severe anaemia patients, per 100 person-years. The data are from the 9 trial locations in Uganda and Kenya (red; data post-discharge (trial) = data from Kwambai *et al.*¹¹). The fitted model (blue; 95% CrI) estimates that the probability of a symptomatic episode per infectious bite declines as the EIR increases (Figure S5). For comparison, the estimated incidence of

uncomplicated malaria by EIR in the general population of under five-year-olds is shown in black for each subnational region (administrative area 1) in malaria-endemic parts of sub-Saharan Africa. (B) As (A) showing hospitalised malaria episodes in the same trial group (log scale). The model-predicted values are the incidence of hospitalised malaria in the general population of children aged 0-5 years for a given annual EIR. Three additional validation data points are shown from separate post-discharge studies (purple; data post discharge (comparison) in Uganda: Opoka *et al.*^{12,13} and Malawi: Phiri *et al.*¹⁰ which were not used for fitting the model.

Impact of PMC across sub-Saharan Africa and burden of repeat SMA

The lower adherence to PMC as measured in a PMC implementation study¹⁸ (Table S2) is estimated to reduce protective efficacy from 86% to 73% during weeks 3-14, resulting in an overall protective efficacy over the 6 months of 39% (as opposed to 46% with perfect adherence). The predicted impact of PMC was greatest in countries with higher transmission intensities, where up to 0.45 malaria-associated readmissions could be prevented per child given PMC (Figure 4A). In just over half of the malaria-endemic countries in Africa, we estimate that less than 10 children need to be given PMC to prevent one hospitalised malaria episode (Figure 4B). In the two highest burden countries, Nigeria and the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC),⁵ only 3.1 and 2.9 children need to be given PMC to prevent a hospitalised episode, respectively (Table 1).

Predictions of total malaria readmissions and deaths averted were sensitive to assumptions about the proportion of malaria cases who access hospital care, and the case fatality rate outside hospital. The following results assume a base scenario where 50% of cases requiring hospitalisation actually access it, and a range is obtained from assuming 30-70% access. If all hospitalised children aged 0-5 years with SMA were given PMC, we estimate that a total of ~36,000 (range 16,000-82,000) malaria-associated readmissions could be prevented per year across all modelled malaria-endemic countries, and 1,870 deaths prevented per year (range 930-3720). Three-quarters of these prevented episodes are in the ten countries that are the focus of the WHO HBHI programme.⁵ In 23 countries (range 19-24 countries), we estimate that less than 100 children need to be given PMC to prevent one death. In Nigeria and the DRC, 55 (range 28-111) and 51 (range 26-103) children need to be given PMC to prevent one death, respectively.

Figure 4. Impact of PMC.

(A) Average number of hospitalised malaria episodes averted per child aged 0-5 years given PMC during the 6 months post-discharge period. (B) Number needed to treat with PMC to avert 1 hospitalised malaria episode. All estimates are shown for subnational (administrative area 1) regions and incorporate imperfect adherence to the three prescribed courses of PMC as observed in ref¹⁸. The assumption in these results is that 50% of cases requiring hospitalisation access hospital care, but there is negligible change in these outputs when this percentage is varied. (C) Total and recurrent SMA episodes with and without PMC. Model estimates are shown in the absence (solid circles) and presence (open circles) of PMC. Recurrent episodes are those occurring within 6 months of a previous SMA episode. PMC is given at 100% coverage to hospitalised cases only and impact largely occurs in the first 3 months post-discharge. We allowed for imperfect adherence to PMC. We assumed that 50% of individuals with SMA reach hospital and varied this for sensitivity analysis (Figure S8). Assuming a low proportion hospitalised results in larger total estimates of SMA burden in the absence of PMC, and smaller total impact of PMC.

The percentage of all SMA episodes which could be prevented by PMC is highly uncertain, given the unknown probability that cases seek care at hospital in different areas, and that the true burden of disease is therefore unknown. We estimate that in the absence of PMC, the burden of recurrent SMA episodes within 6 months of the original episode is 18-27% of the total SMA cases in <5-year-old children in higher transmission settings with EIR>10 (equivalent to slide prevalence in 2–10-year-olds > 25%; Figure 4C), and a lower proportion in lower transmission settings. Weighting by population size, this results in PMC preventing 5-8% of all SMA in under-fives when EIR>10 in the base scenario where 50% are hospitalised, ranging from 3-11% under different assumptions about hospital access (Figure S8).

PMC demand forecast

Using a relationship between EIR and hospitalised SMA incidence based on previous studies in populations with reasonable access to health care,²² and assuming a 7.4% in-hospital case fatality rate,¹⁹ there would be 123,000 (range 54,000-283,000) SMA survivors under five years old per year across all malaria-endemic countries in Africa (Table 1; Figure S9). The highest number of children eligible for PMC would be in Nigeria with 40,000 per year (range 17,000-94,000). In total, the ten high-burden to high-impact countries identified by WHO⁵ would require PMC for 87,000 children per year (range 38,000-201,000). Some countries not on this top-10 list also have high PMC requirements, such as Côte d'Ivoire.

Table 1: Estimated PMC impact and demand in sub-Saharan African countries. The ten high burden countries targeted by the WHO High Burden to High Impact strategy are shown first. Estimates assume 100% PMC coverage and the lower adherence level observed in implementation studies

Country	Population aged under five years	Incidence of hospitalised severe malarial anaemia per 100 person years in 0-5-year-olds without PMC (range*)	Average number of hospitalised malaria episodes prevented per 100 children given PMC	Number of children needed to treat with PMC to prevent one hospitalised malaria episode [†]	Number of children needed to treat with PMC to prevent one malaria death (range) [†]	PMC demand (range)
HIGH BURDEN TO HIGH IMPACT COUNTRIES						
Burkina Faso	3,295,991	0.14 (0.1-0.23)	23.5	4.3	75 (67-88)	2,109 (919- 4,879)
Cameroon	4,237,636	0.21 (0.15-0.35)	18.8	5.3	94 (83-109)	4,176 (1,813- 9,660)
Democratic Republic of the Congo	14,114,883	0.33 (0.24-0.54)	34.7	2.9	51 (45-59)	21,369 (9,346-49,028)
Ghana	4,775,926	0.19 (0.13-0.31)	21.5	4.6	82 (73-95)	4,126 (1,789- 9,500)
Mali	3,215,976	0.08 (0.06-0.13)	9.6	10.4	185 (163-213)	1,197 (520- 2,775)
Mozambique	4,981,850	0.26 (0.19-0.43)	37.6	2.7	47 (42-55)	6,048 (2,651-13,857)
Niger	3,649,415	0.12 (0.09-0.2)	18.9	5.3	94 (82-109)	2,014 (869- 4,670)
Nigeria	33,110,061	0.25 (0.18-0.4)	32.1	3.1	55 (49-64)	37,739 (16,455-86,551)
Tanzania	9,630,285	0.04 (0.03-0.07)	8.3	12.1	215 (193-251)	1,834 (817- 4,406)
Uganda	7,112,378	0.2 (0.15-0.33)	31.7	3.2	56 (49-65)	6,684 (2,920-15,375)
OTHER MALARIA-						

ENDEMIC COUNTRIES						
Angola	4,373,828	0.15 (0.11-0.24)	21.7	4.6	82 (72-95)	2,992 (1,300- 6,910)
Benin	1,934,664	0.39 (0.28-0.64)	37.4	2.7	48 (42-55)	3,502 (1,532- 8,015)
Botswana	288,586	0 (0-0.01)	0.5	215.6	3,826 (3,937-4,629)	4 (2-16)
Burundi	2,039,788	0.11 (0.08-0.18)	17.6	5.7	101 (90-117)	996 (437-2,323)
Central African Republic	880,851	0.36 (0.26-0.59)	38.7	2.6	46 (40-53)	1,480 (648-3,385)
Chad	2,552,929	0.06 (0.05-0.1)	5.9	16.8	298 (265-347)	726 (319-1,720)
Comoros	123,614	0.03 (0.02-0.04)	2.8	35.5	630 (523-707)	15 (6-33)
Cote d'Ivoire	4,094,415	0.35 (0.25-0.57)	34.5	2.9	51 (45-60)	6,560 (2,864-15,031)
Djibouti	151,672	0.01 (0.01-0.02)	0.3	287.2	5,096 (4,653-6,168)	5 (3-15)
Equatorial Guinea	107,080	0.45 (0.33-0.73)	42.8	2.3	41 (37-48)	221 (97-505)
Eritrea	950,825	0.01 (0-0.01)	0.1	723.6	12,840 (14,136-16,176)	25 (8-77)
Ethiopia	18,227,284	0.02 (0.01-0.03)	1	96.5	1,712 (1,469-1,889)	1,274 (622-3,154)
Gabon	288,277	0.27 (0.2-0.45)	25	4	71 (63-82)	364 (158-839)
Gambia	332,684	0.02 (0.02-0.03)	2.5	39.9	708 (661-840)	29 (15-73)
Guinea	2,233,593	0.23 (0.17-0.38)	25.9	3.9	69 (60-79)	2,368 (1,028-5,443)
Guinea-Bissau	329,360	0.04 (0.03-0.07)	5.4	18.6	330 (291-384)	62 (28-149)
Kenya	8,328,699	0.07 (0.05-0.11)	22.2	4.5	80 (72-95)	2,568 (1,143-6,077)
Liberia	788,182	0.4 (0.29-0.65)	40.8	2.5	43 (38-50)	1,443 (632-3,298)
Madagascar	4,315,512	0.03 (0.02-0.05)	3.7	27	479 (421-552)	632 (279-1,512)
Malawi	3,123,362	0.12 (0.08-0.19)	18.3	5.5	97 (85-112)	1,677 (728-3,880)
Mauritania	686,348	0.06 (0.04-0.1)	5.1	19.7	350 (313-409)	191 (85-457)
Namibia	410,614	0.02 (0.02-0.04)	3.4	29.5	523 (466-613)	43 (19-98)
Republic of Congo	830,334	0.24 (0.17-0.39)	24	4.2	74 (65-85)	919 (399-2,117)
Rwanda	2,098,732	0.02 (0.01-0.03)	1.8	56.4	1,000 (886-1,179)	165 (80-441)
Senegal	2,623,405	0.02 (0.02-0.03)	2	49.9	886 (799-1,063)	218 (112-592)
Sierra Leone	1,116,213	0.32 (0.23-0.52)	39.3	2.5	45 (40-52)	1,661 (727-3,798)
Somalia	1,915,090	0.04 (0.03-0.06)	3.2	31.7	563 (503-657)	318 (145-760)

South Africa	6,646,109	0 (0-0.01)	0.2	406.6	7,214 (6,828-8,637)	136 (52-493)
South Sudan	2,260,515	0.17 (0.13-0.29)	20.7	4.8	86 (75-99)	1,813 (788-4,196)
Sudan	6,139,288	0.01 (0.01-0.03)	1.2	85.7	1,521 (1,198-1,815)	400 (142-1,006)
Togo	1,309,796	0.23 (0.16-0.37)	23.5	4.2	75 (66-87)	1,378 (598-3,173)
Zambia	2,970,088	0.08 (0.06-0.13)	19.8	5	90 (79-105)	1,088 (476-2,537)
Zimbabwe	2,841,665	0.01 (0.01-0.02)	0.8	119.4	2,119 (1,841-2,589)	144 (70-380)
TOTAL						122,713 (53,641-283,204)

* range obtained from varying the proportion of cases hospitalised from 30-70%.

† Children are provided with full PMC (3 courses of DP, each containing 3 doses) at discharge, but estimates allow for imperfect adherence in routine settings

Discussion

Our model captures the high burden of repeat malaria episodes requiring hospitalisation within the first six months post-discharge among children recovering from an initial episode of SMA. We estimate that this risk is 23-60 times higher than the average for the population of that age. These repeat episodes constitute an estimated one-fifth to one-quarter of all SMA episodes in high transmission settings. PMC with monthly dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine targets this high-risk group and effectively prevents malaria-associated hospital readmissions or death in trials.^{10,11} We predict that this effect would be notable across most endemic settings in Africa with an effective routine implementation of the intervention.¹⁸ PMC would have the largest impact in the highest transmission and highest burden settings; e.g. in Nigeria and the DRC, where we estimate only 3 children need to be given PMC to prevent a hospitalised malaria episode. However, we estimate that in most areas fewer than 10 children need to be given PMC to prevent one hospitalised malaria episode. This dynamic is partly driven by the ‘self-targeting’ nature of PMC – that only high-risk children admitted to hospital will receive the treatment (unlike other forms of chemoprevention, which are administered to all healthy children in a particular age range). Our analysis also suggests PMC is highly cost-effective across a wide range of settings, given that the cost of inpatient malaria care in sub-Saharan Africa is \$15.64-\$137.87.²⁶ However, cost-effectiveness will depend on the local costs of clinical management and the organisation of health care services.

The risk of hospitalised malaria remained high over a prolonged period, with the incidence still being 23-36 times higher than the average for the age group, 4-6 months post-discharge. Earlier studies suggested that haematological recovery after severe anaemia requires around six weeks.⁹ However, our findings suggest that recently discharged children remain at higher risk than the general population well beyond this period. Since the PMC intervention effect is largely restricted to the first 14 weeks, providing longer protection may have significant health impacts. Future studies should assess the benefit of augmenting PMC with additional prevention strategies against malaria such as longer courses of chemoprevention, malaria vaccines, or monoclonal antibodies that provide at least six months of protection. Caregivers in the PMC trials were encouraged to use insecticide-treated nets, but the provision of a new effective insecticide-treated net might have higher impact. Older children with SMA also have notable post-discharge morbidity, therefore increasing the eligible age range might also increase total impact.

Our results on the number of cases averted per child given PMC and the number needed to treat to avert adverse outcomes were derived from clinical trial results and are relatively robust to assumptions about hospital access. However, the total demand for PMC and the number of cases and deaths that could be prevented are uncertain, given the lack of data on the probability of accessing hospital care. Access to hospitals is likely to vary greatly between and within countries.²⁰ A recent study tracking severely ill children in the community in Uganda, Nigeria, and DRC found that 41-65% go on to access hospital care. Care seeking for repeat episodes of malaria after hospital discharge during the trial was probably better than in routine clinical practice because participants were financially remunerated for their travel expenses and may have had greater awareness of malaria danger signs. Our analysis finds that PMC has a lower total impact when many children with SMA do not access hospital care. However, we find that the benefit per child given PMC is greater in areas where children are less likely to return to the hospital for subsequent episodes, due to the high burden of repeat severe malaria and its high case fatality rate in the absence of hospital care. This is also important given that poor households can incur catastrophic health expenditure for severe malaria.²⁷

Our finding that around 18-27% of hospitalised SMA episodes would occur within six months of the original episode is plausible considering previous hospital-based studies of children with severe anaemia. In Uganda, 75% of children with severe anaemia had been hospitalised within the previous six months for SMA.²⁸ In the PMC trial in Kenya and Uganda, 35% of children had been hospitalised previously for severe disease of any cause.¹¹ We found that children with SMA are probably exposed to infectious mosquito bites more frequently than the average child, because the incidence of symptomatic malaria post-discharge was higher than the expected incidence of infectious bites in this age group in some settings (Figure S6). The probability of developing infection and symptoms per infectious bite is also higher than in other children.²⁹ The group who develop SMA may have particular frailty to malaria for genetic or biological reasons.³⁰

Our model was able to replicate the observed total number of hospitalised and uncomplicated malaria episodes in the post-discharge trials. We estimated a relationship between EIR and both outcomes, although there was considerable variation around this in the data. There is uncertainty

in the EIR values, which are based on predicted prevalence estimates from a geospatial model.¹⁵ Uncertainty in the incidence of post-discharge episodes also arises from small sample sizes in some hospitals, as well as some misclassification of uncomplicated malaria. One outlier was Kamuli mission hospital in Uganda, which was predicted to have a high EIR yet showed a relatively low incidence of post-discharge hospitalised malaria. This hospital is a private not-for-profit facility, where admitted patients usually incur relatively higher out-of-pocket payments than patients at public hospitals. Trial personnel reported that some malaria cases that would otherwise have been hospitalised were treated as out-patient cases with injectable artesunate to avoid hospital costs and were therefore classified as uncomplicated malaria cases (personal communication, author A. Dhabangi).

In summary, our findings support the widespread implementation of PMC in malaria-endemic countries in Africa, particularly high-burden countries. In countries with low burden, this consideration is likely to be influenced by intervention costs, which may be considered in economic evaluation. However, the total impact of PMC is heavily dependent on the proportion of SMA cases that can access hospital care and the successful delivery of dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine. Further, the high risk of malaria morbidity persists for at least six months post-discharge, suggesting the need for longer-acting interventions.

Author contributions

ATM and LCO: Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Writing - Original Draft, Visualisation, Writing - Review & Editing. **ACG and MC:** Conceptualisation, Writing - Review & Editing, Funding acquisition. **FOTK, KP and BR:** Conceptualisation, Writing - Review & Editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Supervision. **CK, TKK, AD, TNG, RO, AM, RI, MJK, TCDL and DJW:** Data curation, Validation, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing.

Declaration of interests

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

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Projected health impact of post-discharge malaria chemoprevention among children under the age of five years with severe malarial anaemia in Africa: a modelling analysis

Supplementary Information

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Post-discharge cohort model

We initially considered using an existing well-established malaria transmission model to describe the incidence of hospitalised malaria post-discharge.¹ However, initial analysis indicated that the high incidence of uncomplicated and hospitalised malaria after an severe malarial anaemia (SMA) episode, as observed in trials and clinical studies,²⁻⁴ was not adequately captured using this model, despite allowing for individual variation in immunity and exposure to mosquito bites. A novel model was therefore created to estimate the increased risk in the post-discharge population and how it changes over time and with varying malaria transmission intensities.

We developed a compartmental model to describe the incidence of uncomplicated and hospitalised malaria among the trial cohort of children aged 6–59 months during the six months post-discharge follow-up period in PMC and placebo trial arms. The model has the following states: prophylaxis (P_{AL} and P_{DP}), susceptible (S), treated uncomplicated malaria (T_U), and treated hospitalised malaria (T_S) (Figure 1, main text). State transitions are described in the main text and we provide further details here. The equations are below.

Children are given artemether-lumefantrine (AL) at the time of hospital discharge to clear remaining parasites, which provides a period of prophylaxis against reinfection. They therefore enter the model into a protected state P_{AL1} on the first day of their treatment. We modelled this initial period of AL protection as gamma-distributed with an average of 13 days based on previous analysis of reinfection during clinical trials of AL.⁵ The probability of leaving state P_{AL1} on day t_d after discharge is therefore:

$$r_{pAL}(t_d) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(k_{AL})} \gamma\left(k_{AL}, \frac{t_d}{v_{AL}}\right) - \frac{1}{\Gamma(k_{AL})} \gamma\left(k_{AL}, \frac{t_d - 1}{v_{AL}}\right)$$

where k_{AL} and v_{AL} are the shape and scale parameters of the gamma distribution, respectively. The equation gives the integral of the gamma distribution between the start and end of day t_d . The number of children leaving state P_{AL1} each day is therefore: $r_{pAL}(t_d - 1)P_{AL1}(0)$ where P_{AL1} is P_{AL1} at $t_d = 0$.

Prophylaxis prevents the emergence of blood stage infections from the liver but does not prevent infection with sporozoites, nor liver-stage infection. After the AL prophylaxis wanes, children move to a susceptible state S . We assume a constant force of infection, and therefore a constant rate of new blood stage infection, rather than explicitly including a latent period, in line with previous work.⁵ That is, children can experience a malaria episode as soon as they transition to the susceptible state.

We model the incidence of both uncomplicated and more severe episodes of malaria requiring hospitalisation in the cohort. Hospitalised cases can include those who meet a stricter WHO definition of severe malaria as well as those who do not,⁶ in line with the outcome metric in the post-discharge chemoprevention (PMC) trial² used for fitting the model. The total incidence of these symptomatic episodes occurs at a rate equal to the product of the local entomological inoculation rate (EIR), the probability that an infectious bite leads to infection b , the probability of developing symptoms of clinical disease (total uncomplicated and severe) ϕ and the relative exposure to mosquito bites among the post-discharge group of children ξ (Table 1, main text). Because we only observe the incidence of symptomatic malaria, these parameters are not individually identifiable and so we estimate them as a product $b\phi\xi$. We assume that each infectious bite can only cause one symptomatic episode. We do not track asymptomatic infections and those without symptoms remain in the S state, which represents those susceptible to clinical malaria disease.

We further allow that the risk of symptomatic malaria per infectious bite could decline over time since hospital discharge, based on results from the PMC trial and other post-discharge studies, and the

hypothesis that recovery will reduce vulnerability. We estimated the rate of the decline by allowing total incidence in the cohort to be scaled by a Weibull survival curve:

$$e^{\left[-\left(\frac{t}{\lambda_{risk}}\right)^{\eta_{risk}}\right]}$$

where t is the time since hospital discharge and the scale and shape parameters λ_{risk} and η_{risk} , are estimated.

Furthermore, the probability that an infectious bite leads to infection and symptoms are both known to decline with EIR in the general population. We included this possibility by further scaling symptomatic malaria incidence by a similar functional form to that identified in previous analyses^{7,8} of the relationship of EIR and the probability of symptomatic malaria:

$$e^{-wE}$$

and estimated the parameter w , since the relationship is unknown in this post-discharge population. The total incidence of symptomatic malaria in the placebo group inc_d at a given local EIR, and a given time since discharge t_d is therefore:

$$inc_d(t_d) = EIR b\phi\xi e^{\left[-\left(\frac{t_d}{\lambda_{risk}}\right)^{\eta_{risk}}\right]} e^{-wEIR}$$

Upon developing symptoms, we allowed a two-day delay for treatment seeking ($1/r_{UM}$), after which uncomplicated cases (state T_U) receive 13 days of AL post-treatment prophylaxis (dur_{PAL}) as described above. This 15-day period was modelled as a fixed duration (dur_{TU}), both for computational efficiency and because AL is estimated to have a sharp drop off in protection rather than a gradual decline (Figure S1). We assumed all symptomatic malaria episodes during follow-up were treated with AL in both trial arms, since study clinics were set up and financial reimbursement was given to cover costs of treatment seeking² (probability of treatment $f_T = 1$). The drug efficacy, i.e. the probability of successful parasite clearance and protection after AL is denoted e_{AL} . Recovered cases return to the S state. The proportion of uncomplicated cases who fail treatment ($1 - e_{AL}$) remain in the S state and their episode is also counted in the model output. A proportion θ of the total symptomatic malaria cases require hospitalisation. These enter a treated severe state T_S with a fixed duration of 18 days in total (dur_{TS}), which includes 2 days treatment seeking, a mean hospital stay of 3 days (dur_H) based on the trial data² and 13 days of AL prophylaxis post-discharge.

We track children in the PMC trial arm separately and denote their states: S' , P'_{AL1} , T'_U , T'_S . The model describing these children is the same as the placebo group except for additional PMC protection against uncomplicated and hospitalised episodes. PMC is given as three full courses of dihydroartemisinin-piperaquine (DP) starting at the beginning of weeks 2, 6 and 10 post-discharge. Each course contains 3 doses of DP, so that the full PMC intervention contains 9 doses in total. The efficacy of DP is denoted e_{DP} . We modelled DP prophylaxis as a probability of prevention of reinfection, p_{pDP} that declines over time since treatment, using a Weibull-survival function with a mean of 28 days based on previous fitting to clinical trial data:⁹

$$p_{pDP}(t_{PMC}) = p_{ad}e_{DP}e^{\left[-\left(\frac{t_{PMC}}{\lambda_{DP}}\right)^{\eta_{DP}}\right]}$$

where t_{PMC} is the time since the last PMC treatment, p_{ad} is the probability of adhering to the current course of DP while λ_{DP} and η_{DP} represent the scale and shape parameters of the Weibull distribution. The efficacy of DP is high (99%) and adherence during the trial is also high (97.3-99.0%). During

model fitting we therefore chose to simply reduce the probability of protection proportionately to the efficacy and adherence (as shown in the equation above) for computational efficiency, rather than separately track children who do not receive protection from one of the DP courses. We allowed for different adherence to each of the 3 courses of PMC $p_{ad1}, p_{ad2}, p_{ad3}$. We incorporated the measured percentage of children adhering to treatment in the trial setting² when fitting to the trial data (Table 1, main text). For simplicity, we assumed that for each course of PMC, caregivers either gave all 3 doses or none, which was relatively consistent with observations during implementation (only 1.5% of children received 1-2 doses of DP per treatment course, with the remainder taking all or none). The partial protection is applied to all children in the PMC intervention group, except children in states T_U and T_S (currently symptomatic and treated). When children leave the T_U and T_S states and return to S , we assume they have the same protection as those who did take PMC. This approximately captures the trial recommendation that children should take PMC once recovered from their symptomatic episode,³ although it was not possible to explicitly include multiple PMC timings outside the standard trial times due to computational constraints.

We further explored whether the probability of a symptomatic malaria episode being severe enough to require hospitalisation, θ , could be different in children with active PMC drug protection (θ_2) compared to children without (θ_1). We defined active drug protection as inhibitory drug levels providing $>1\%$ probability of protection.

In the model, we incorporated the number of children recruited in each trial site to each trial arm, and the loss to follow up in each group. At the time a child was lost to follow up (due to leaving the study, or dying) we reduced the total population accordingly in all model states in that trial site and arm. E.g. if there were 100 children on day $t_d - 1$, and 99 on day t_d , we multiply the numbers in all model states on day $t_d - 1$ by 0.99 to obtain the numbers still present on day t_d .

The model was written in discrete time using daily time steps, with t_d being the time since hospital discharge. The cohort model is run for 25 weeks to match the follow up duration in the data. All rates were converted to daily transition probabilities using the equation:

$$y = 1 - e^{-r}$$

where y is the transition probability and r is the daily rate.¹⁰ The incidence of all symptomatic episodes per day, inc_d , was converted to the probability of an episode by the end of the day y_d .

The full system of equations for the placebo group is as follows:

$$P_{AL1}(t_d) = P_{AL1}(t_d - 1) - r_{pAL}(t_d - 1)P_{AL1}(0)$$

$$\begin{aligned} S(t_d) = & S(t_d - 1) + r_{pAL}(t_d - 1)P_{AL1}(0) - y_d(t_d - 1)e_{AL}S(t_d - 1) \\ & + y_d(t_d - dur_{TU})e_{AL}S(t_d - dur_{TU})(1 - \theta_1) \\ & + y_d(t_d - dur_{TS})e_{AL}S(t_d - dur_{TS})\theta_1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_U(t_d) = & T_U(t_d - 1) + y_d(t_d - 1)e_{AL}S(t_d - 1)(1 - \theta_1) \\ & - y_d(t_d - dur_{TU})e_{AL}S(t_d - dur_{TU})(1 - \theta_1) \end{aligned}$$

$$T_S(t_d) = T_S(t_d - 1) + y_d(t_d - 1)e_{AL}S(t_d - 1)\theta_1 - y_d(t_d - dur_{TS})e_{AL}S(t_d - dur_{TS})\theta_1$$

The system of equations for the PMC intervention group is:

$$P'_{AL1}(t_d) = P'_{AL1}(t_d - 1) - r_{pAL}(t_d - 1)P'_{AL1}(0)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
S'(t_d) &= S'(t_d - 1) + r_{pAL}(t_d - 1)P'_{AL1}(0) - y_d(t_d - 1)e_{AL}S'(t_d - 1)(1 - p_{DP}(t_{PMC})p_{ad}) \\
&\quad + y_d(t_d - dur_{TU})e_{AL}S'(t_d - dur_{TU})(1 - \theta)(1 - p_{pDP}(t_{PMC})p_{ad}) \\
&\quad + y_d(t_d - dur_{TS})e_{AL}S'(t_d - dur_{TS})\theta(1 - p_{pDP}(t_{PMC})p_{ad}) \\
T'_U(t_d) &= T'_U(t_d - 1) + y_d(t_d - 1)e_{AL}S'(t_d - 1)(1 - \theta)(1 - p_{pDP}(t_{PMC})p_{ad}) \\
&\quad - y_d(t_d - dur_{TU})e_{AL}S'(t_d - dur_{TU})(1 - \theta)(1 - p_{pDP}(t_{PMC})p_{ad}) \\
T'_S(t_d) &= T'_S(t_d - 1) + y_d(t_d - 1)e_{AL}S'(t_d - dur_{TS})\theta(1 - p_{pDP}(t_{PMC})p_{ad}) \\
&\quad - y_d(t_d - 18)e_{AL}S'(t_d - dur_{TS})\theta(1 - p_{pDP}(t_{PMC})p_{ad})
\end{aligned}$$

At $t_d = 0$, all individuals in the placebo arm start in state P_{AL} and all individuals in the PMC arm start in state P'_{AL1} . The protection from PMC, p_{pDP} , is 0 before day 14. The time since PMC, t_{PMC} , is $t_d - 14$ between follow up days 14-42, $t_d - 42$ between day 42-70, and $t_d - 70$ thereafter. The proportions of children adhering to PMC p_{ad} during these 3 time periods are p_{ad1} , p_{ad2} and p_{ad3} , respectively (Table S1). The probability of a symptomatic episode being more severe and requiring hospitalisation, θ , is θ_2 when the child is protected by DP with probability of protection $p_{pDP} > 0.01$ and θ_1 when $p_{pDP} \leq 0.01$.

Model fitting and validation

We obtained prior estimates for the EIR in the areas surrounding each hospital in the post-discharge studies. Since EIR is not a commonly measured metric, we generated modelled EIR from the average of parasite prevalence estimates in 2-10 year olds within a 20 km radius of each hospital using our pre-existing transmission model^{23,25}. These parasite prevalence estimates are from the Malaria Atlas Project (MAP) global map averaged over the years 2016-2018, when the trial was conducted. We used these EIR estimates as semi-informative prior medians, assuming a gamma distribution with 10% coefficient of variation (Table S1).

As described above, we estimated the total incidence of uncomplicated plus hospitalised malaria episodes as the product of the local EIR, the probability that an infectious bite leads to infection b , the probability of symptoms (total uncomplicated and severe) ϕ and the relative exposure to mosquito bites among the post-discharge group of children ξ (Table 1). Children usually experience lower exposure to bites than adults simply due to having lower body surface area.^{23,24} However, it is unknown whether exposure among the post-discharge group is higher or lower than among other children of the same age in the general population. During the initial analysis we noticed that the maximum incidence of symptomatic malaria in the post-discharge children could be slightly higher than the expected average EIR, and hence we introduced the term ξ allowing a different exposure in this group of children. We set the prior for $b\phi\xi$ to be a uniform distribution between 0 and 2, so that the maximum incidence could not be more than 2-fold higher than the average EIR.

We also estimated the unknown parameters describing the relationship between the risk of an episode per infectious bite, EIR and time post-discharge described above (λ_{risk} , η_{risk} , w) using weakly informative priors (Table S1).¹¹ The parameters describing the proportion of episodes requiring hospitalisation in children without PMC and with active PMC protection (see above), θ , were given a uniform prior between 0-1.

We fit to incidence data from weeks 1-25 of follow up and excluded the final week of follow up (week 26) due to anomalous results. The recorded incidence of uncomplicated malaria was much

higher in the last week of follow up than in any other week and was a clear outlier (Figure S7). This was driven by cases from the trial site in Jinja only. Model fitting was undertaken using MCMC in the Stan software. We ran 4 chains, each having 5,000 burn-in and 10,000 sampling iterations. We assessed convergence through visualisation of posterior distributions and the Gelman-Rubin's convergence diagnostic.¹²

Population modelling of PMC demand and impact in different epidemiological settings

To estimate PMC demand and impact in different geographic areas, we combined information from the following databases and models. Modelled estimates were used due to the lack of complete primary country-level data.

- 1) Incidence of hospitalised SMA in the general population of 3 month -9 year olds in relation to parasite prevalence, as modelled by Paton *et al*¹³ based on data from Kenya, Tanzania and Uganda.
- 2) Parasite prevalence in 2-10 year olds in country subnational regions from the Malaria Atlas Project.^{14,15}
- 3) The incidence of uncomplicated and hospitalised malaria in 0-5 year olds in the 6 months after discharge from hospital following a severe anaemia episode, in relation to EIR, from our current analysis of the Kwambai *et al*² study (Figures 2 & 3, main text).
- 4) A well-established transmission model^{1,7,16} (Imperial College London; 'IC model'). This was used to translate between key metrics in the above model inputs: (a) EIR and prevalence in 2-10 year olds, (b) the incidence of SMA in 0-5 year olds relative to 0-10 year olds. This model has been calibrated against a wide range of epidemiological data,⁸ including hospitalised malaria incidence in different transmission settings and age groups.¹ The hospitalised malaria component was previously fitted to incidence data from nine sites in different African countries where populations were considered to have good transport networks to hospital and lived a maximum of 19 km away.¹ The model was also calibrated to hospitalised SMA data.

We constructed a population model tracking SMA in all under five year olds which incorporated the different sources of information 1-4 (Figure S2). The post-discharge cohort as described above was embedded within this model, and we also allowed for additional detail and factors that are different outside the trial setting. These include the possibility of not going to hospital and not receiving effective treatment for uncomplicated malaria. The model also allows that SMA increases risk of future SMA in an iterative process, which results in episodes being more concentrated in particular individuals. We stratify the population of under five year olds into 'low-risk': those who have not experienced an SMA episode in the last 6 months, and 'high-risk': those who have had SMA and are at higher risk of subsequent malaria episodes. We now refer to the latter group as 'post-SMA' rather than 'post-discharge', since they may not all have accessed hospital care for the original episode. We further stratify the model into groups depending on the different number of PMC doses received. We assume that the high-risk post SMA group is described well by the post-discharge cohort model above. That model was calibrated to data on severe anaemia patients who did not all have malaria, however this group without malaria was a minority (15% of the cohort).

Children transition through the model as follows. Those in the low-risk group, i.e. who have not experienced SMA in the past 6 months, are in state G and new SMA episodes occur in this group at rate inc_{gSMA} . SMA cases have a probability of accessing hospital care, p_H . Those who are hospitalised enter state H with a fixed 3-day stay in hospital and have a probability of dying, q_{SMAH} . Those who survive then follow a near-identical process to those in the post-discharge cohort model

described earlier. We assume that all hospitalised individuals receive AL at discharge as per standard severe malaria guidelines and we model this as a fixed 13-day period of protection in state P_{AL1} . Children who do not receive PMC follow the same path as those in the post-discharge cohort model placebo group described previously. Children who receive PMC but do not then take the first dose enter state S_H (susceptible, previously received PMC). That is, they experience new symptomatic malaria episodes at rate inc_d , dependent on EIR and time since discharge. The trial settings only included areas with transmission intensity up to EIR of around 30 per year (Figure 3, main text). Since the relationship between EIR and post-discharge incidence of malaria is unknown for higher EIRs, we assumed that post-discharge incidence would plateau at EIR=30 and not increase further nor decrease in higher transmission settings (only 3.8% of regions modelled have an estimated EIR>30). During these episodes children have a probability of requiring hospitalisation θ and a probability $1 - \theta$ of having uncomplicated malaria that only requires an outpatient visit. In contrast to the trial setting, we assume the proportion of children receiving treatment for uncomplicated episodes f_T , is <100%. Likewise, of those who would have been hospitalised in the trial, the proportion p_H who access hospital care now is <100%. Given lack of data on the probability of accessing hospital care, we assume p_H is the same for lower risk and higher risk children, and for different types of severe malaria. We vary the assumed value of p_H from 30-70% based on the recent CARAMAL study tracking children with suspected severe malaria in community settings.¹⁷ We also assume that the probability of hospitalisation is not related to previous hospitalisation status. If children access hospital care they enter state T_S as above, or if they receive AL for uncomplicated malaria they enter state T_U . After fixed durations they return to the susceptible S_H state.

In this population model, episodes of SMA occur at many time points and children enter the post-SMA state at different times, unlike in the cohort model described above. In order to track the time since SMA for the purpose of modelling changing risk, we separated the children in the high-risk groups into daily compartments from week 3 (when they enter the susceptible state after AL protection ends) up to 25 weeks post-SMA, resulting in 161 high risk days (n_{HR}). We assume the percentage of episodes requiring hospitalisation which have SMA during this time (p_{SMA}) is the same as during the trial² (SMA episodes / total hospitalised malaria episodes = 44%). Those who experience recurrent SMA during the high-risk period once again have probability of hospitalisation p_H and subsequently return to the beginning of the high-risk period. After 25 weeks, children return to the low-risk G state if they have not experienced any more SMA episodes.

PMC is given to hospitalised children at discharge with probability z_{PMC} , which describes PMC coverage. The probabilities of adherence to each of the 3 PMC courses on days 14, 42 and 70 post-discharge are p_{ad1} , p_{ad2} and p_{ad3} . We assumed the same adherence as observed during a recent PMC implementation trial in Malawi,¹⁸ where all 3 PMC courses were given to caregivers at the time of discharge from hospital without further adherence reminders (Table 1, main text). Children could therefore miss a PMC course, for example, taking PMC course 1 at day 14 and course 3 at day 70, but missing the day 42 course. However as above, we assume they do not take partial PMC courses (e.g. 1 dose of DP instead of the full course of 3 doses). Children receiving PMC have a probability of protection against reinfection provided by DP which changes by day since treatment according to the Weibull survival curve described earlier. We stratify the model according to the different PMC courses that children may receive. For example, children enter state PMC_1 if they get the first course or remain in the susceptible high-risk state S_H if not. From these states, they then transition to state PMC_2 only if they receive the second PMC course, and state PMC_3 only if they receive the third course. For example, children who only received the first course would remain in state PMC_1 , where the probability of protection declines to zero over time, so that children in this state eventually acquire the same risk as those with no PMC in state S_H (at the equivalent time after the original SMA episode). The probability of protection at time j since discharge in states PMC_1 , PMC_2 , and PMC_3 is denoted p_{pDP1} , p_{pDP2} and p_{pDP3} .

A proportion of SMA cases ($1 - p_H$) do not access hospital care and they enter state D_C (disease in the community). Those who survive enter the susceptible high-risk post-SMA state S_C (susceptible, community, did not receive PMC) at the same time that those who were hospitalised enter the susceptible state S_H post-discharge. Little is known about disease progression outside hospital. Due to lack of data, we do not model any recurrent malaria episodes in state D_C . This assumption has no effect on the comparison of the modelled scenarios with and without PMC intervention since SMA cases outside hospital would be unaffected by PMC. Children who are hospitalised with SMA and do not receive PMC also enter state S_C after their period of AL protection is ended.

We explicitly model mortality from SMA and from other types of hospitalised malaria during the 25-week post-SMA period. The case fatality rate of SMA in hospital is $Q_{SMAH}=7.4\%$ based on a meta-analysis of hospital data.^{19,20} We allow that only a proportion of other malaria inpatients usually meet the WHO severe malaria case definition criteria.⁶ Since the severity of patients who are hospitalised may vary between settings, we use an in-hospital case fatality rate of 1% based on country reports from Kenya and Uganda, where the trial was carried out.^{6,21} Of note, this is lower than the case fatality rate of ~9% for hospitalised patients who meet the WHO case definition of severe malaria.²⁰ Case fatality rates outside hospital are highly uncertain. We follow the approach of Camponovo *et al.*⁶ who triangulated verbal autopsy malaria mortality data in the community with severe malaria incidence. In their analysis the case fatality rate of malaria outside hospital is approximately double that within hospital, and therefore we assume a case fatality rate of 14.8% for non-hospitalised SMA cases and 2% for other cases. In order to keep a constant population size, new individuals are added to the G state at the same rate as the total mortality rate.

The full system of equations for the population model at time t is below. It was coded using discrete daily time steps to be consistent with the post discharge cohort model. All children begin in state G at time 0 and then the model is run to equilibrium. The high risk, post-SMA states $S_H, S_C, PMC_1, PMC_2, PMC_3, T_S, T_U$ are 2D arrays containing the number of individuals in the state at time t and day j .

The total SMA cases at time t is:

$$C_{SMA}(t) = y_{gSMA}G(t-1) + \sum_{j=1}^{n_{HR}} y_d(j)p_{SMA} \left[\theta_1 S_H(t-1, j) + \theta_1 S_C(t-1, j) + \sum_{k=1}^3 (1 - p_{pDPk}(j)) \theta PMC_k(t-1, j) \right]$$

where θ is the risk of developing disease requiring hospitalisation among symptomatic cases and is equal to θ_1 or θ_2 depending whether the probability of protection from DP is currently less than or more than 0.01 in each PMC state. y_{gSMA} is the risk of having a new SMA episode per day in the G state, calculated from inc_{gSMA} in the same way that y_d was calculated from inc_d above.

The total number of other malaria cases without severe anaemia who require hospitalisation in the high-risk group at time t and on day j is then similarly:

$$C_S(t, j) = y_d(j)(1 - p_{SMA}) \left[\theta_1 S_H(t, j) + \theta_1 S_C(t, j) + \sum_{k=1}^3 (1 - p_{pDPk}(j)) \theta PMC_k(t, j) \right]$$

We do not track non-SMA severe cases in the general population, since we are specifically interested in the effect of SMA in increasing future risk, and there is no specific evidence that other types of severe malaria do so. The equations for the state variables are:

$$G(t) = G(t-1) - y_{gSMA}G(t-1) + (1 - y_d(n_{HR}))(S_H(t-1, n_{HR}) + S_C(t-1, n_{HR}) + PMC_1(t-1, n_{HR}) + PMC_2(t-1, n_{HR}) + PMC_3(t-1, n_{HR})) + T_U(t-1, n_{HR}) + T_S(t-1, n_{HR}) + p_H(q_{SMAH}C_{SMA}(t-1) + q_H C_S(t-1)) + (1 - p_H)(q_{SMAC}C_{SMA}(t-1) + q_C C_S(t-1))$$

$$H(t) = H(t-1) + p_H(1 - q_{SMAH})C_{SMA}(t-1) - p_H(1 - q_{SMAH})C_{SMA}(t - dur_H)$$

$$D_C = D_C(t-1) + (1 - p_H)(1 - q_{SMAC})C_{SMA}(t-1) - (1 - p_H)(1 - q_{SMAC})C_{SMA}(t - dur_{TS})$$

$$P_{AL}(t) = P_{AL1}(t-1) + p_H(1 - q_{SMAH})C_{SMA}(t - dur_H) - p_H(1 - q_{SMAH})C_{SMA}(t - dur_{TS})$$

For $j=0$:

$$S_H(t, 0) = p_H(1 - q_{SMAH})z_{PMC}(1 - p_{ad1})C_{SMA}(t - dur_{TS})$$

$$S_C(t, 0) = [p_H(1 - q_{SMAH})(1 - z_{PMC}) + (1 - p_H)(1 - q_{SMAC})]C_{SMA}(t - dur_{TS})$$

$$PMC_1(t, 0) = p_H(1 - q_{SMAH})z_{PMC}p_{ad1}C_{SMA}(t - dur_{TS})$$

$$PMC_2(t, 0) = PMC_3(t, 0) = T_U(t, 0) = T_S(t, 0) = 0$$

The state variables at time t and on day j since entering the high-risk state are as follows. We use indicator variables i_j which are 1 on day j and 0 otherwise. i_{PMC2} and i_{PMC3} are indicator variables that are 1 on the days that the 2nd or 3rd course of PMC begins, and 0 otherwise, and p_{ad} is p_{ad} , p_{ad} and p_{ad} for the 1st, 2nd and 3rd courses of PMC.

For $j>0$:

$$S_C(t, j) = S_C(t-1, j-1) - y_d(j-1)\theta_1 p_{SMA}(t-1)S_C(t-1, j-1)$$

$$-y_d(j-1)(1 - \theta_1)f_{TeAL}S_C(t-1, j-1)$$

$$-y_d(j-1)\theta_1(1 - p_{SMA})[p_H + (1 - p_H)(1 - q_C)f_{TeAL} + (1 - p_H)q_C]S_C(t-1, j-1)$$

$$+y_d(j - dur_{TU})(1 - \theta_1)f_{TeAL}S_C(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU})$$

$$+y_d(j - dur_{TS})\theta_1(1 - p_{SMA})p_H(1 - q_H)S_C(t - dur_{TS}, j - dur_{TS})$$

$$+y_d(j - dur_{TU})\theta_1(1 - p_{SMA})(1 - p_H)(1 - q_C)f_{TeAL}S_C(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU})$$

$$S_H(t, j) = S_H(t-1, j-1) - y_d(j-1)\theta_1 p_{SMA}(t-1)S_H(t-1, j-1)$$

$$-y_d(j-1)(1 - \theta_1)f_{TeAL}S_H(t-1, j-1)$$

$$-y_d(j-1)\theta_1(1 - p_{SMA})S_H(t-1, j-1)[p_H + (1 - p_H)(1 - q_C)f_{TeAL} + (1 - p_H)q_C]$$

$$+y_d(j - dur_{TU})(1 - \theta_1)f_{TeAL}S_H(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU})$$

$$+y_d(j - dur_{TS})\theta_1(1 - p_{SMA})p_H(1 - q_H)S_H(t - dur_{TS}, j - dur_{TS})$$

$$+y_d(j - dur_{TU})\theta_1(1 - p_{SMA})(1 - p_H)(1 - q_C)f_{TeAL}S_H(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU})$$

$$-i_{PMC2} p_{ad2} S_H(t-1, j-1)$$

$$-i_{PMC} p_{ad3} S_H(t-1, j-1)$$

$$PMC_1(t, j) = PMC_1(t-1, j-1) - y_d(j-1)\theta p_{SMA}(t-1)PMC_1(t-1, j-1) \left(1 - p_{pDP1}(j-1)\right)$$

$$- y_d(j-1)(1-\theta)f_T e_{AL} PMC_1(t-1, j-1) \left(1 - p_{pDP1}(j-1)\right)$$

$$- y_d(j-1)\theta(1-p_{SMA})PMC_1(t-1, j-1) \left(1 - p_{pDP}(j-1)\right) [p_H + (1-p_H)(1-q_C)f_T e_{AL}$$

$$+ (1-p_H)q_C]$$

$$+ y_d(j - dur_{TU})(1-\theta)f_T e_{AL} PMC_1(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU}) \left(1 - p_{pDP1}(j - dur_{TU})\right)$$

$$+ y_d(j - dur_{TS})\theta(1-p_{SMA})p_H(1-q_H)PMC_1(t - dur_{TS}, j - dur_{TS}) \left(1 - p_{pDP}(j - dur_{TS})\right)$$

$$+ y_d(j - dur_{TU})\theta(1-p_{SMA})(1-p_H)(1-q_C)f_T e_{AL} PMC_1(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU}) \left(1$$

$$- p_{pDP1}(j - dur_{TU})\right)$$

$$- i_{PMC2} p_{ad2} PMC_1(t-1, j-1)$$

$$- i_{PMC3} p_{ad3} PMC_1(t-1, j-1)$$

$$PMC_2(t, j) = PMC_2(t-1, j-1) + i_{PMC} p_{ad2} (PMC_1(t-1, j-1) + S_H(t-1, j-1))$$

$$- y_d(j-1)\theta p_{SMA}(t-1)PMC_2(t-1, j-1) \left(1 - p_{pDP}(j-1)\right)$$

$$- y_d(j-1)(1-\theta)f_T e_{AL} PMC_2(t-1, j-1) \left(1 - p_{pDP2}(j-1)\right)$$

$$- y_d(j-1)\theta(1-p_{SMA})PMC_2(t-1, j-1) \left(1 - p_{pDP2}(j-1)\right) [p_H + (1-p_H)(1-q_C)f_T e_{AL}$$

$$+ (1-p_H)q_C]$$

$$+ y_d(j - dur_{TU})(1-\theta)f_T e_{AL} PMC_2(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU}) \left(1 - p_{pDP}(j - dur_{TU})\right)$$

$$+ y_d(j - dur_{TS})\theta(1-p_{SMA})p_H(1-q_H)PMC_2(t - dur_{TS}, j - dur_{TS}) \left(1 - p_{pDP2}(j - dur_{TS})\right)$$

$$+ y_d(j - dur_{TU})\theta(1-p_{SMA})(1-p_H)(1-q_C)f_T e_{AL} PMC_2(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU}) \left(1$$

$$- p_{pDP}(j - dur_{TU})\right)$$

$$- i_{PMC} p_{ad} PMC_2(t-1, j-1)$$

$$PMC_3(t, j) = PMC_3(t-1, j-1)$$

$$+ i_{PMC} p_{ad3} (S_H(t-1, j-1) + PMC_1(t-1, j-1) + PMC_2(t-1, j-1))$$

$$- y_d(j-1)\theta p_{SMA}(t-1)PMC_3(t-1, j-1) \left(1 - p_{pDP}(j-1)\right)$$

$$- y_d(j-1)(1-\theta)f_T e_{AL} PMC_3(t-1, j-1) \left(1 - p_{pDP}(j-1)\right)$$

$$- y_d(j-1)\theta(1-p_{SMA})PMC_3(t-1, j-1) \left(1 - p_{pDP}(j-1)\right) [p_H + (1-p_H)(1-q_C)f_T e_{AL}$$

$$+ (1-p_H)q_C]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& +\gamma_a(j - dur_{TU})(1 - \theta)f_{TeAL}PMC_3(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU})\left(1 - p_{pDP3}(j - dur_{TU})\right) \\
& +\gamma_a(j - dur_{TS})\theta(1 - p_{SMA})p_H(1 - q_H)PMC_3(t - dur_{TS}, j - dur_{TS})\left(1 - p_{pDP3}(j - dur_{TS})\right) \\
& +\gamma_a(j - dur_{TU})\theta(1 - p_{SMA})(1 - p_H)(1 - q_C)f_{TeAL}PMC_3(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU})\left(1 - p_{pDP}(j - dur_{TU})\right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$T_U(t, j) = T_U(t - 1, j - 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& +\gamma_a(j - 1)(1 - \theta)f_{TeAL}\left[S_H(t - 1, j - 1) + S_C(t - 1, j - 1) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \sum_{k=1}^3 \left(1 - p_{pDPk}(j - 1)\right)PMC_k(t - 1, j - 1)\right] \\
& -\gamma_a(j - dur_{TU})(1 - \theta)f_{TeAL}\left[S_H(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU}) + S_C(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU}) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \sum_{k=1}^3 \left(1 - p_{pDPk}(j - dur_{TU})\right)PMC_k(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU})\right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$T_S(t, j) = T_S(t - 1, j - 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& +(p_H(1 - q_H) + (1 - p_H)(1 - q_C)f_{TeAL})C_S(t - 1, j - 1) \\
& -p_H(1 - q_H)C_S(t - dur_{TS}, j - dur_{TS}) \\
& -(1 - p_H)(1 - q_C)f_{TeAL}C_S(t - dur_{TU}, j - dur_{TU})
\end{aligned}$$

Population model calibration and simulation

We calibrated the model of SMA in the whole population to different epidemiological settings as follows. For each subnational region of Africa, we obtained the parasite prevalence in 2-10 year olds from the Malaria Atlas project 2019 map,^{14,15} and from this, estimated EIR using the IC transmission model.⁷ We estimated the total incidence of hospitalised SMA for each area in children aged 3 months-9 years using the recent relationship with parasite prevalence published by Paton *et al.*¹³ To convert this to incidence of hospitalised SMA in 0-5 year olds, we generated the ratio of SMA incidence in 3 month-9 year olds to 0-5 year olds in each parasite prevalence category (binned to the nearest 0.1% prevalence) using the IC transmission model. To obtain this ratio, the relationship of IC model-predicted SMA incidence with prevalence was smoothed using LOESS methods.

We calibrated the model for each geographic area so that the total hospitalised SMA incidence was equal to the Paton *et al* estimate. We did this by varying the incidence of SMA in the low-risk children in the *G* state using the *optim* function in R.²² Given uncertainties about the probability of accessing hospital care, we varied the assumed percentage of cases eligible for hospitalisation who would have accessed hospital care in the Paton *et al.* settings between 30, 50 and 70%. Likewise we

then varied the proportion of cases accessing hospital care in all countries from 30-70%, so that the incidence of hospitalised SMA could be lower, the same, or higher than the Paton *et al* estimates for a given parasite prevalence (from 0.4-fold lower to 2.3-fold higher). We assumed that 50% of uncomplicated malaria episodes would have been treated in the settings studied in Paton *et al*, based on household survey data.²³ We ran the model in the presence and absence of PMC for each subnational area and estimated PMC impact by comparing the two outputs.

Figure S1. Drug protection against reinfection over time in placebo and PMC trial arms in fully drug-adherent patients, using drug protection profiles estimated previously.^{5,9} Left: placebo arm individuals receive one course of AL at discharge i.e. day 0. Right: PMC arm individuals additionally receive three courses of DP beginning at days 14, 42 and 70 post-discharge. Neither arm receives any further chemoprevention for the last months of follow up.

Figure S2. Incidence of SMA per 1000 person-years. Incidence in 3 month-9 year olds is plotted as in an original publication by Paton *et al.* Incidence in 0-5 year olds was estimated using the Paton *et al.* result combined with the relative incidence of SMA by age in the IC model (see supplementary text for details).

Figure S3. Population model of SMA in all under five year olds.

Figure S4. The incidence of symptomatic malaria (uncomplicated & severe) declines over time since discharge. We plot the incidence of symptomatic malaria in the post-discharge cohort relative to EIR in adults (the term $b\phi\xi$ in Table S1, i.e. the probability that an infectious bite leads to infection b , the probability of developing symptoms of clinical disease (total uncomplicated and severe) ϕ , and the relative exposure to mosquito bites among the post-discharge group of children ξ).

Figure S5. The incidence of symptomatic malaria (uncomplicated & severe) increases with EIR but the incidence per infectious bite is estimated to decline as EIR increases. We plot the relative incidence of symptomatic malaria per bite in the post-discharge cohort relative to EIR in adults (the term $b\phi\xi$ in Table S1, i.e. the probability that an infectious bite leads to infection b , the probability of developing symptoms of clinical disease (total uncomplicated and severe) ϕ and the relative exposure to mosquito bites among the post-discharge group of children ξ).

Figure S6: EIR in 0-5-year olds versus observed total incidence of symptomatic malaria in 0-5 year old children per person per year in post-discharge studies, without PMC. EIR in 0-5-year olds is estimated to be 36% of that experienced by adults, as established in previous studies.^{8,24} Symptomatic malaria includes both uncomplicated (UM) and severe malaria (SM). Data are from the 9 trial hospitals in Kwambai *et al.*² (K) and validation studies by Opoka *et al.*(O)^{4,25} described in the main text. The dashed line indicates the expected relationship if each bite led to a symptomatic malaria episode, and children who have recently had SMA have the same exposure to infectious bites as the average child in the 0-5 year age group. Usually only a fraction of infectious bites results in an infection in the body, and only a fraction of these lead to symptoms.^{8,26} The observed relationship suggests children experiencing SMA are more highly exposed to bites than the average child, and/or are more likely to become infected when bitten and experience symptoms.

Figure S7. Cumulative number of uncomplicated and hospitalised malaria cases over time since initial hospital discharge in the PMC trial. The upper lines in each plot show cases in the placebo group, while the lower lines are cases in the PMC intervention group. The final week highlighted in orange is an outlier with an unexpected number of uncomplicated cases in both trial and placebo arms. These higher numbers occurred just in one trial site in Jinja. We fit the model to incidence in weeks 1-25, excluding the final week 26.

Figure S8. Sensitivity analysis of main text Figure 4C: varying the proportion of cases hospitalised. Assumptions are: (A) 30% of SMA cases were hospitalised in the Paton *et al.* study, to which the baseline incidence of SMA in this model was calibrated, and 70% of cases are hospitalised in the currently modelled setting; (B) 50% of cases hospitalised in Paton *et al.* and 50% in current model, as in main text Figure 4C; (C) 70% of cases hospitalised in Paton *et al.* and 30% in current model. The total number of cases changes but the relative contribution of post-discharge cases to total disease burden in the absence of PMC remains similar. PMC has most impact in the scenario where we assume a low proportion hospitalised in Paton *et al.* and a higher proportion in the current model.

Figure S9. Forecasted PMC demand: the estimated number of treatments required per year per 100 children aged 0-5 years in subnational (admin-1) regions of malaria-endemic countries. Calculations based on incidence of hospitalised SMA in 0–5-year-old children, assuming a 7.4% in-hospital case fatality rate. Panels A, B and C show the lowest, base scenario and highest forecasts of demand, respectively, based on varying assumptions about the proportion of patients with SMA that access hospital.

Table S1: Model parameters: post discharge cohort model.

Parameter	Description	Prior	Posterior value (95% CrI) or fixed value	Source
<i>EIR</i>	Annual EIR in adults for each trial site	gamma median (95% CI)		Source of prior means ^{14,16}
	Siaya	28.0 (22.8-33.8)	28.2 (23.3, 33.8)	
	Kisumu	5.9 (4.8-7.1)	5.4 (4.4, 6.4)	
	Homa Bay	14.5 (11.8-17.5)	10.9 (8.8, 13.5)	
	Migori	2.0 (1.7-2.4)	2.5 (2.1, 2.9)	
	Jinja	13.8 (11.3-16.7)	18.2 (15.6, 21.0)	
	Hoima	7.9 (6.5-9.6)	5.5 (4.5, 6.6)	
	Masaka	4.7 (3.9-5.7)	5.1 (4.3, 6.1)	
	Mubende	4.9 (4.0-6.0)	5.3 (4.4, 6.3)	
	Kamuli	28.8 (23.5-34.8)	26.2 (18.5, 36.4)	
<i>b</i>	Probability of successful mosquito-to-human transmission per infectious bite in post-discharge period	-	Estimated as part of the product $b\phi\xi$	-
ϕ	Proportion of new infections that are symptomatic	-	Estimated as part of the product $b\phi\xi$	-
ξ	Exposure to infectious bites in post-discharge cohort relative to EIR in adults	-	Estimated as part of the product $b\phi\xi$	-
$b\phi\xi$	Maximum relative incidence of symptomatic malaria in post discharge cohort relative to EIR in adults	Uniform (0,2)	1.05 (0.65, 1.85)	This analysis
<i>w</i>	Rate parameter for the relationship of EIR with probability of symptomatic malaria post-discharge	Half normal (0.0, 1.0)	0.030 (0.016, 0.044)	This analysis
θ_1	Probability of requiring hospitalisation post-discharge among symptomatic malaria cases, not under active PMC protection*	Uniform (0,1)	0.39 (0.36, 0.42)	This analysis

Parameter	Description	Prior	Posterior value (95% CrI) or fixed value	Source
θ_2	Probability of requiring hospitalisation post-discharge among symptomatic malaria cases, under active PMC protection*	Uniform (0,1)	0.25 (0.17, 0.34)	This analysis
λ_{risk}	Scale parameter describing the decline in incidence over time post discharge	Half normal (0, 500)	103.9 (32.6, 168.3)	This analysis
η_{risk}	Shape parameter describing the decline in incidence over time post discharge	Half normal (0, 500)	0.70 (0.38, 1.31)	This analysis
f_T	Proportion of symptomatic children who access antimalarial treatment	fixed	1 (in post discharge trial)	Assumption
$1/r_{UM}$	Days until treatment sought after developing first symptoms of malaria	fixed	2	
e_{AL}	Efficacy of AL at clearing parasites	fixed	0.98	²⁷
e_{DP}	Efficacy of DP at clearing parasites	fixed	0.99	²⁷
dur_{TU}	Duration in state T_U , days	fixed	15	^{5,19}
dur_{TS}	Duration in state T_S , days	fixed	18	^{2,5,19}
dur_{PAL}	Duration of post-treatment prophylaxis provided by AL	fixed	13	⁵
dur_H	Duration of time in hospital for severe malaria, days	fixed	3	²
p_{ad1} p_{ad2} p_{ad3}	Adherence: proportion taking each course of PMC drugs in the trial setting 1 st course 2 nd course 3 rd course	fixed fixed fixed	1 0.985 0.973	²

Parameter	Description	Prior	Posterior value (95% CrI) or fixed value	Source
k_{AL} v_{AL}	Duration of protection after AL treatment, gamma-distributed			5
	Shape parameter	fixed	93.5	
	Scale parameter	fixed	0.139	
λ_{DP} η_{DP}	Duration of protection after DP treatment, Weibull-distributed			9
	Scale parameter	fixed	28.1	
	Shape parameter	fixed	4.4	
inc_d	Incidence of symptomatic episodes of malaria per person per day (uncomplicated + more severe) post-discharge	variable		-
$y_d(t_d)$	Probability of a symptomatic malaria episode per person per day (uncomplicated + more severe) at time t_d post-discharge	variable		-
$p_{protectDP}$	Probability of protection against re-infection by DP by day since treatment	fixed, dependent on time since treatment		-

Table S2: Additional model variables and parameters used in the full population model of SMA that are not already covered in Table S1.

Variable or parameter	Description	Value	Source
$C_{SMA}(t)$	Number of new SMA cases on day t	Variable	current analysis
$C_S(t)$	Number of new, severe non-SMA cases on day t (cases eligible for hospitalisation) in the high risk post-SMA states	Variable	current analysis
γ_{gSMA}	Probability of a symptomatic malaria episode per person per day (uncomplicated + severe) in the G state	Variable	current analysis
n_{HR}	Number of days in the high risk state from weeks 3-25 after discharge	161	current analysis
p_{SMA}	Probability of having SMA among severe episodes post-discharge	0.44	²
p_H	Probability of severe cases accessing hospital care	Varied: 0.3, 0.5, 0.7	¹⁷
z_{PMC}	PMC coverage: proportion of children given PMC at hospital discharge	1	assumed
f_T	Proportion of symptomatic children who access antimalarial treatment	0.5 Outside trial settings	²³
q_{SMAH}	Case fatality rate: hospitalised SMA	7.4%	²⁰
q_{SMAC}	Case fatality rate: non-hospitalised SMA	14.8%	derived from ^{6,20}
q_H	Case fatality rate: hospitalised non SMA severe malaria	1.0%	⁶
q_C	Case fatality rate: severe malaria non-hospitalised	2.0%	derived from ⁶
	Adherence: proportion taking all 3 doses of each course of PMC drugs during routine implementation 1st course (day 14) 2nd course (day 42) 3rd course (day 70)	 0.765 0.879 0.894	¹⁸

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